

Problems and Prospects of Tourism Industry in Bangladesh: A Case of Cox's bazar Tourist Spots

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ABSTRACT

Tourism is an important driver of economic growth. Tourism is one of the most rising industries all over the world. Bangladesh is a country filled with natural wonders and world heritage places. There are many popular tourist spots in Bangladesh. Among them, Cox'sbazar is considered as one of the most widely visited and rising tourist spots in our country but there has not been enough research, planning, advertisement and implementation for the development of this area. The key aim of this paper is to identify problems and prospects of tourism at Cox'sbazar tourist spots which can be more convenient for all aspect of the tourists in the world. This study has conducted through semi-structured questionnaire and by the existing literature to collect relevant data. Based on data and analysis, study has found out several major problems such as lack of infrastructure facilities, modern and sufficient recreation facilities, proper training, proper planning from Government, marketing and updated information, security and safety, involvements of non-professional peoples, political instability, visa problems which is constraint to develop Cox'sbazar tourism. This study also has explored twelve popular tourist spots in the Cox'sbazar district. Basically, this study focused on the attractive tourist spots of Cox'sbazar and finally provided some suggestions to overcome those problems.

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1. Introduction

People move from one place to another on their vacation. They try to explore the natural loveliness which can be kept their mind quiet and spend their time delightful, Tourism sector always buds on the necessity of people when moving crossways inside and outside of the country. Nowadays, the tourism industry is increasing and playing a great contribution to GDP growth as well as economic development of the country. Globalization accelerates this rapid expansion of the tourism industry across the world. According to the World Travel and Tourism Council Annual Updates, travel & tourism's direct contribution to world GDP and employment, supporting over 292 million jobs and generating 10.2% of global GDP in 2016. This continued growth in tourism business throughout the world is encouraging and nations are becoming more concern to attract more tourists to their own destinations and trying to promoting this sector as a major source for the economic development of the nation (Ibid). Tourism is going to be the key economic sector for the developing countries and similar to Bangladesh. Every year it achieves a huge amount from the tourism sector to directly contribute to its GDP.

Bangladesh is a country filled with natural wonders and untouched reserves and home to a variety of unique and magnificent creatures. With hills, valleys, forests, beaches, lakes, and rivers, eco-tourism in Bangladesh is a model. Although, this is still a new relatively form of tourism in Bangladesh. Bangladesh is also full of natural beauty; Rivers, coasts, and beaches, archaeological sites, religious places, hills, forests, waterfalls, and tea gardens surround it. The Sundarban, Historic Mosque in the city of Bagerhat, Ruins of Buddhist Vihara at Paharpur are the three world heritage sites in Bangladesh among 1007. To observe the beauty of nature, huge amount of local and foreign tourists visit the country and its tourist attraction sites. Tourism is a travel for recreation, religious, leisure, family or business purposes, usually for a limited duration. There are many popular tourist destinations in Bangladesh. Among them, Cox's Bazar is considered one of the most widely visited tourist destinations in our country. At the head of this territory is Cox's Bazar which is as romantic as its name is to the outside world. It has a different name as known as by the name "Panowa", the exact translation of this name "yellow flower". It's another old name was "Palongkee". The latest Cox'sbazar derives its name from Captain Cox (died 1798), who was an army officer and as his name as it named Cox'sbazar. The Cox's Bazar has a small town and it is a capital city of tourists. The municipality covers an area of 6.85 sq. with 12 wards and has a population of 167,477. It is situated in the southeast of the country and has the longest Sea beach in the world. It is Located at a distance of 152 km. South of Chittagong, Cox's Bazar is connected both by air and road with Dhaka and Chittagong. The major source of economy of Cox's Bazar is tourism. Many people are involved in these hospitality and customer service type business. A number of people are also involved in fishing and collecting seafood and sea products for their livelihood. Conventionally Cox's Bazar is a conservative society and socio-cultural and economic statistics including literacy rate is far below than national average. The main attractions of Cox'sbazar included; the world's longest Sea beach (120 km), Himchari picnic spot which is 8km distance from Cox'sbazar, Inani Beach which is 35km away from the city, Sonadia Island, Teknaf peninsula about 80km from town and graphical Sant Martin Island to the south at 13kms distance from mainland. Above all these places are simply reachable from Cox'sbazar town by bus, jeep, and Ship on the way of water. As result, Cox'sbazar becomes a favor of tourism.

Tourism in Bangladesh is managed and controlled by the Bangladesh Parjatan Corporation (BPC) under the Ministry of Civil Aviation and Tourism. The economic contribution of tourism and the share of Cox'sbazar to the national economy are not studied with reliable statistics. According to the World Travel and Tourism Council's Bangladesh Country Report 2017 (www.wttc.org) forecasted that the tourism generates the direct contribution to GDP and it was BDT840.2 billion (USD10.6 billion), 4.3% of total GDP in 2016 and it is forecast to rise by 7.2% in 2017 and to rise by 7.1% per annum to BDT1.783.0billion (USD22.6billion), 4.7% of total GDP in 2027. The total contribution to the employment sector, it was 3.8% of total employment (2187, 000 jobs). This is expected to rise by 2.7% in 2017 to 2,247,000 jobs and rise by 1.8per annum to 2,695,000 jobs (1.6% of total employment) in 2027. There were visitor exports generated BDT 11.1billion (USD140. 0mn), 0.4% of total exports in 2016 exports in 2016. This is forecast to grow by 11.2% in 2017 and grow by 7.6% per annum, from 2017-2027 to BDT25.6billion (USD324.2mn) in 2027, 0.5% or total. Travel and tourism investment in 2016 was BDT72.5billion, 1.2% of total investment (USD0.9billion). It should rise by 13.9% in 2017, and rise by 9.3%per annum over the next ten years to BDT201.8billion (USD2.6billion) in 2027, 1.8% of total investment. Near five million people visit Cox'sbazar in every year (Mr. Md. Rezaul Karim, Chairman, Cox'sbazar Tourists Club Limited in the interview on 26.03.2018). Tourists come mainly from all parts of Bangladesh. The basic itinerancy of visitors includes the walk along the beaches, sea bathing, shopping from the Rakhaine stalls. The beaches of Labonee, Kalatoli, Himchari and Inani are particularly heavily visited-Labonee beach is reportedly one of the most heavily visited tourist destination in the country (Daily maximum visitors as high as 30,000) (Abdullah Z Ahmed, 12 August 2006). The area from Labonee to Kalatali beach has many hotels, motels, cottage, rest and guest houses and restaurants, around 300 in number developed by both private and government for tourist. Thousands of local and non-local Bangladeshi nationals are working in the tourism sector of Cox's Bazar. The rural setting of Cox's Bazar is gradually changing by the force of tourism. But there has not been enough research, planning, advertisement and implementation for the development of this area. Taking into consideration the researcher attempts to identify and analyze "The Problems and Prospects of Tourism Industry in Bangladesh: A Case of Cox's-Bazar Tourist Spots".

2. Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to discuss the problems and prospects of tourism in the Cox'sbazar. More especially the other objectives are below;

- To analyze the present scenario of the tourism industry in Bangladesh.
- To identify the different attractive tourist spots in the Cox'sbazar for analyzing the opportunities.
- To find out the obstacles to developing tourism in Cox'sbazar and provide some recommendations to overcome these problems.

3. Research Methodology

The study is basically descriptive in nature and based on both primary and secondary data. These methods used to collect information relevant to reach the research objectives. The secondary data collected from the relevant published books, different previous journal, research works, newspaper, magazines, and reports of various government authorities,

various websites and Wikipedia. Researchers have also conducted the interview through semi-structured questionnaire and a visit during the period of January-April'2018 to collect the relevant information to find out the problems of tourism at Cox'sbazar. Different officials of Bangladesh Government, local people, domestic and foreign tourists have been interviewed to obtain the relevant data. This research will be helpful for the future researcher to get data.

4. Literature Review

Tourism is an important and dynamic sector for the world economy and to developing country like Bangladesh (Chowdhury, Fahim, & Dooty, 2013). For many developing and underdeveloped country in the world, tourism has occurred as a major income driving industry. As a promising alternative tourism sector along with the export sector has a positive effect on economy like employment generation, impacts on the expansion of linked industries, and poverty alleviation (Khondker & Ahsan, 2015). Any initiative by government and tourism authority has a positive impact on tourism and the arrivals to the tourist (Karambakuwa, et al., 2011). The Tourism industry of Bangladesh can contribute to achieving the vision of Bangladesh for 2021, by investing short, mid, and long term projects with sufficient budgetary allocation (Parveen, 2013). Tourist can be attracted by making the information about the tourism sector available to the tourist (Nabi & Zaman, 2014).

Some other studies have been conducted on tourism industry in Bangladesh by Hossain and Firozzaman (2003), Alam and Shamsuddoha (2003), Shamsuddoha (2005), Hossain (2006) and Lincoln (2008). These studies enumerated the significance of tourism industry from the many angles like economic, social, cultural, political, etc. Shah Azam, et al, conducted a study on factors affecting in choosing Bangladesh as a tourist destination. The study shows that service quality, natural beauty, security, and shopping facility are statistically significant in explaining the intention to select a tourist destination in Bangladesh. Some other studies have been conducted in this field by Sofique and Parveen (2009), Ahammed (2010), Rahman (2010), Hasan & Shanewaz (2014), Prodip Dey, Uddin & Hasan (2013) which are directly related to Cox's Bazar tourism regarding economic and socio-cultural effect of tourism. Their studies were not only about Cox'sbazar sea beach, Inani beach, and Saint Martin Island, but also some attractive tourist spots were considered as famous and popular spots in Cox'sbazar district. So far researchers of this study know that there is no rich study which has been conducted yet covering the understanding of existing image of Sea beach tourism in Bangladesh especially Cox's Bazar as a world longest sea beach as well as tourist destination and its attractive spots. So this study is an attempt to explore the present condition and prospect of tourism in Cox'sbazar and examine the problems existed in this district. This study also explores some new and popular tourist spots which can be more attractive for tourists where they can come to visit and enjoy a lot.

5. Discussion

This study tried to cover and discuss on the current status of tourism industry in Bangladesh, contribution of this sector to GDP, problems, and prospects of Cox'sbazar tourism and suggested to overcome the identified barriers in this study.

5.1 Current Status of Tourism in Bangladesh

Bangladesh received a large number of amounts during the last sixteen years from tourism sector. According to the World Travel and Tourism Council's Bangladesh Country Report

2017 (www.wttc.org) supported that the tourism generates the direct contribution to GDP and it was BDT840.2 billion (USD10.6 billion), 4.3% of total GDP in 2016 and it is forecast to rise by 7.2% in 2017 and to rise by 7.1% per annum to BDT1.783.0billion (USD22.6billion), 4.7% of total GDP in 2027. The total contribution to employment sector, it was 3.8% of total employment (2187, 000 jobs). This is expected to rise by 2.7% in 2017 to 2,247,000 jobs and rise by 1.8per annum to 2,695,000 jobs (1.6% of total employment) in 2027. There were visitor exports generated BDT 11.1billion (USD140. 0mn), o.4% of total exports in 2016 exports in 2016. This is forecast to grow by 11.2% in 2017 and grow by 7.6% per annum, from 2017-2027 to BDT25.6billion (USD324.2mn) in 2027, o.5%or total. Travel and tourism investment in 2016 was BDT72.5billion, 1.2% of total investment (USD0.9billion). It should rise by 13.9% in 2017, and rise by 9.3%per annum over the next ten years to BDT201.8billion (USD2.6billion) in 2027, 1.8% of total investment.

Figure1: Tourist Arrivals in Bangladesh since 2001-2016

Source: World Tourism Organization and Yearbook of Tourism

Statistics

Figure 2: Income from Bangladesh Tourism since 2001-2016

Source: World Tourism Organization and Yearbook of Tourism

Statistics

The country is trying from the inception of this industry to attracting more tourists to its destinations and to earn more foreign currency from this sector. The statistics on this industry shows that both the arrivals and earnings from tourism in Bangladesh have increased over the past.

5.2 Attractive Tourism Destination of Cox'sbazar

Cox'sbazar is the capital for tourists in Bangladesh. There have world longest sea beach, forest hills on a shoreline, delightful conch, golden sand beach, waterfall, old Buddhist monasteries, island, wildlife sanctuary and many other attractive tourists' spots in Cox'sbazar, which are easily accessible by bus, jeeps, and ship on the way of the sea. According to Rahman (2007), he studied that the Bangladesh is fast developing an interesting tourist spot on the global map. Our tourist attractions are spreading widely countrywide. The country's historical legacy is collected of various strands, including Islamic, Hindu, Buddhist, and so on. However, major tourist's attractions of Cox's Bazar (tourist's capital of Bangladesh) are discussed below:

- **Laboni Beach:** This is the main beach and most beautiful beaches of Cox's Bazar. It is considered the main beach as the fact that it is closest to the town where we can see the natural beauty. Close to the beach, there are hundreds of small shops selling souvenirs and beach accessories to the tourists. Always this beach is crowded by the tourists, visitors, surf, jog, cycle, and swim.
- **Kolatoli Beach:** This is an attractive beach for the tourists and it is situated in Cox'sbazar. Every year different age's people come here to enjoy the taking sea bath. Tourists can take the sea bath, driving sea boat, and taking fresh and moving various kinds of seafood. Walking besides the seashore on moon light is very pleasant for all tourists.
- **Himchari:** It is another most attractive tourist's spot in Cox'sbazar. It is located about 18 km south of Cox's Bazar, along the beach. This place is famous as a picnic spot and film shooting. It is also famous for its waterfalls and the road to Himchari runs between the open sea on one side and hills on another side which always makes the journey to Himchari very attractive and more pleasant.
- **Inani Beach:** This is also one of most beautiful beaches which are Located 35 km south of Cox'sbazar; this white sandy beach is located within Ukhia Thana. It is famous for its golden sand and cleans shark free water which is ideal for sea bathing. Most of the tourists prefer to come down here for relaxing because it is free from the crowd of tourists that is usually seen at the Laboni beach. Inani beach attracts most of the tourist who appreciates the wonders of beautiful nature. More attraction is fringed with tall palm trees swaying gently in the breeze and has a calm lagoon which is perfect for the little ones to paddle in. sitting on the rock and coral bounders with the warm waves lapping on the shore around you, as they have done for millions of years, can be a very rewarding experience. Seashells of all shapes, colors and sizes are found along Inani beach, making beach combing popular entertainment.
- **Ramu:** This is about 16km away from Cox'sbazar and is located on the road to Chittagong. There is a village with a sizeable Buddhist population which is famous for its handicrafts and homemade cigars. Also there are monasteries, khyangs, and pagodas containing

images of Buddha in gold, bronze and other metals inlaid with precious stones. One of the most interesting of these temples is on the bank of the Baghkhali River. The people and village have a charm of its own.

- **Aggmeda Khyang Monastery:** This is also a beautiful place for tourist in the Cox'sbazar and it is a large Buddhist monastery. This place is respected by around 400,000 Buddhist people of Cox's Bazar; and the Chittagong Hill Tracts. The key sanctuary is posted on a series of round timber columns. It has a prayer chamber and an assembly hall along with a repository of a large of small bronze Buddha images and a number of old manuscripts.
- **Ramu Cantonment:** One of the new tourist spots is Ramu Cantonment in Cox'sbazar and it is going to popular place in Bangladesh. This Army cantonment is situated in the southern part of Bangladesh at Ramu Upazila, Cox'sbazar. This is a new military station which hosts the newly formed 10th Infantry Division. Ramu Cantonment is strategically important and currently necessary infrastructures are being built to host various units and brigades. Every day a large number of visitors are coming to visit this famous spot from different district of Bangladesh.
- **Sonadia Island:** There are many Islands in Cox'sbazar, One of them Sonadia Island and it is situated about 9 km north-west of Cox'sbazar. It is small and very rich for various kinds of shells. The western side of the island is sandy and different kinds of shells are found on the beach. On the northern part of the island, there are beds of window pane oysters. This Island is famous for dry fish and the fishermen build up temporary camps during the winter season for drying sea fishes.
- **Maheshkhali:** Maheshkhali is an island, which is a coast of Cox'sbazar and it has an area of 268 square Kilometers. This island offers panoramic scenic beauty and is covered by low hills (about 300 feet high) and mangrove forests. The shrine of Adinath, a temple of Shiva, and a Buddhist Pagoda are also there located.
- **Teknaf:** Teknaf is a bordered side between Bangladesh and Myanmar and southern point of Country. It is about 80 km far from Cox'sbazar town and is a memorable experience as the road goes alongside the beautiful Naf River and through forested hilly roads.
- **St. Martin's Island:** St. Martin Island is one of the attractive Islands for tourists and is situated south-west of the southern tip of the Cox'sbazar-Teknaf peninsula. It is the most beautiful and coral island in Bangladesh where tourists come to enjoy their moments with calm. It is a small (around 10km) island with beaches fringed with coconut palms and bountiful marine life. This island can help the tourist to purify their souls by the fresh air and smoothing. It is away from Teknaf around 30 km and tourist can go there by Keri Sindabad or another Sea Truck and motorboat. It is about 8 km west of the northwest coast of Myanmar at the mouth of the Naf River. The local name of the island is "Narical Gingira Janjina/Jinjera", Bangla, meaning Coconut Island' ([http:// en.wikipedia.org /wiki/Cox's_Bazar](http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cox's_Bazar)).
- **Dulhazra Safari Park:** This safari park is an extension of an animal sanctuary and is another attractive tourists spot in Cox'sbazar. It is located in Chakaria upazila along the Chittagong-Cox'sbazar road about 50 km far from Cox'sbazar town and 107 km away from the Chittagong port city. The sanctuary was developed on a hillside area of about 2,224

acres. In this Safari Park, There people come to watch animals in the natural state where animals are moving freely in large areas. There are domesticated elephants which are available for a ride and other animal attractions include lions, Bengal tigers, Crocodiles, Bears, Chitals and lots of different types of birds and monkeys.

From the above analysis, it can be said that the tourism industry of Bangladesh in general and Cox's Bazar spot, in particular, has great potentials both as a foreign exchange earner and provider of job opportunities with the resultant multiplier effect on the country's economy as a whole.

5.2 Problems of Tourism at Cox'sbazar

There is some potential spot to improve as a very expected tourist destination in Cox'sbazar. But tourism industry of Cox'sbazar has been facing multisided problems. It mainly lacks proper planning and infrastructure facilities, law and order system (corruption & terrorism) etc. However, according to the findings of this study and previous researches, the following are the main barriers of tourism development of Cox's bazar:

5.2.1 Lack of Infrastructure Facilities

Current status of infrastructure facilities is not developed in Cox'sbazar. For this reason in spite of the presence of many tourism potentials, Bangladesh's share of income from tourism is very poor. With poor infrastructure, little marketing sense and direction, and a national carrier too busy serving the labor traffic, tourism potentials of Bangladesh this far remained untouched. One of the key aspects of infrastructure is the availability of monetary funds during travel. Even until recently, the ATMs outside Dhaka aren't connected to the international network, and traveler's cheques are very difficult to cash.

5.2.2 Lack of Modern and Sufficient Recreation Facilities

Although Cox's Bazar Spot is treated as a tourism capital of Bangladesh, its recreation facilities yet to developed. Existing recreation facilities are not modern and sufficient according to the demand of the tourists especially for foreign tourists. For example, boating, wind surfing, horse racing and other modern playing instruments with local recreation facilities etc. are not available in the Cox's Bazaar and other tourism spots of Bangladesh.

5.2.3 Lack of Security and Safety

Security and safety is the most important thing for tourism development in any tourism spot like Bangladesh. Cox'sbazar is one of important destination for tourist, but in this place, the security system is not to develop yet. Sometimes it creates more problems for tourist due to kidnapping and hijacking issues. In the midnight tourists cannot move to tourists spot especially Cox'sbazar sea beach, because they can attack by the hijacker or band. In 2013, the Bangladesh Government formed the tourist police unit for tourist zone at Cox'sbazar. They are trying to serve safety and security for the local and international tourists but it is not enough, that's why foreign tourists are disagreeing to stay a longer period in Cox'sbazar. This issue leads to loss huge foreign currencies of the country. Moreover, due to lack of sufficient security foreign tourists rarely stay in the beach area after evening time to enjoy the rare natural beauty (during sunset) without any anxiety.

5.2.4 Political Instability

Bangladesh is a democratic country and every five years changes its government by the election. After and before election period violates all the political parties countrywide, at that time domestic and international tourist afraid to move to the tourist destination. Due to political instability Bangladesh loss, a huge amount of currency and tourism industry suffer significantly as well.

5.2.5 Involvement of Non Professional Peoples

Non-professional peoples are involving in tourism business; this is the one of the important problem at Cox'sbazar tourism. When the tourism sector earns more profit in other countries than our country faces problem by the non-professional staffs. So the government needs to ensure professional people's involvement in a related sector to promote our tourism sector.

5.2.6 Lack of Proper Training and Human Resources Related to Tourism

Developed human capital is key asset for any industry, trained up human resources always play an important role to develop it. Tourism industry is a key sector to increase GDP in any region like Bangladesh. In this regard, Bangladesh Parjatan Corporation has established National Hotel Tourism Training (NHTTI) in 1974. A two-year diploma course on Hotel-Management has been started in 2002. However, the above initiatives of BPC are not sufficient to meet the needs of all tourist spots in the country. Besides, some recent research findings (Siddiqui 2006), (Rahman 2007), (Parveen 2009), (MD Kamrul Hassan, 2013), and (Khondker & Ahsan 2015) proved that still there is acute shortage of tourism experts in most hotels and motets of tourist areas in Bangladesh. But now in Cox'sbazar established a private University where are two years diploma course on Hotel Management already started.

5.2.7 Visa Problems

Visa policy of the government is one of the main reasons behind the foreign tourists' reluctance to visit Bangladesh. If the government lifts visa restrictions for visitors from Europe, USA, and other western countries, around 20 lakh foreign tourists will come to Bangladesh in a couple of years. Now it requires about 15 to 20 days for a Bangladeshi visa even for a European citizen (The Daily Star, May 29, 2008).

5.2.8 Lack of Proper Planning from Government

According to the World Travel and Tourism Council's Bangladesh Country Report 2017 (www.wttc.org) supported that the tourism generates the direct contribution to GDP and it was BDT840.2 billion (USD10.6 billion), 4.3% of total GDP in 2016 and it is forecast to rise by 7.2% in 2017 and to rise by 7.1% per annum to BDT1.783.0billion (USD22.6billion), 4.7% of total GDP in 2027. It is a global report but in Bangladesh no reliable report, data or statistics on tourism are available. But this assumed investment how, when and where will be invested are not clear. All policy, planning and moneys are allocated for already established as tourist organization. Now "Cox'sbazar Development Authorities" is trying to develop tourism industry of Cox'sbazar. There is no extra planning or budget allocation for the development of Cox'sbazar to establish as a popular tourists spot. So the Government should provide special facilities to both local & foreign investors to invest in this industry considering its economic growth and development. The Government may give the Tax holiday to more and more development of tourism industry and set up hotels and restaurants in the tourist areas all over the country especially Cox'sbazar as a longest sea beach. As a result, foreign investors will be interested to invest in this industry.

5.2.9 Lack of Marketing and Updated Information

Cox'sbazar is one of the important districts for tourist destination and is definitely needs to be advertised properly on the popular tourist related websites. There should be coordination of information and services between these websites and popular hotels, restaurants, shops and travel services of Cox's Bazaar and other tourist spot s of Bangladesh. We need to take pragmatic steps to develop and updated our websites to increase international tourist flow. It also needs to share update information in popular websites and advertise in different ways. For instance, Cambodia has its tourism websites in eight languages; Thailand, Malaysia, Indonesia in 12 languages, and we have ours only in one language, English.

6. Recommendations and Conclusion

6.1 Recommendations

- The Government should take proper planning to develop infrastructural of the Cox'sbazar tourist spots by the maintaining international standards.
- The Government should take initiatives by organizing such types of training program related to tourism to develop human resources for local people, and also should create awareness among them to protect natural beauties.
- Tourist spots should be peaceful, untouched but it should have relaxing, fun, exciting, safe and secured, educative, informative and exact information of tourists spot should be delivered to the visitors.
- It must be needed to create effective and participative working network between public and private sectors in tourism, and local people should be involved with them.
- The Government should make a tourist information center and it can be introduced the Cox'sbazar for the tourist. They can get update information about their expected spots, transference and located place and essential information.
- In abroad mission, we can send our tourist bulletin, brochures and magazines related on tourism to inspire international officials to visit Cox'sbazar as a world longest sea beach and popular tourist zone.
- Government should provide special facilities to both local & foreign investors to invest in Cox'sbazar for infrastructural development like hotel-motel, restaurant and shopping center.
- Medical center should be established by the government in every tourist spot to ensure medical services.
- Cox'sbazar should be introduced by the websites to visit it as an "Explore the natural beauty and longest sea beach".

So that are no so far that Cox'sbazar is the next prospective tourist spot from where Bangladesh can earn huge amount of foreign currency.

6.2 Conclusion

The objective of this study to analyze the beautiful and attractive location of Cox'sbazar and it is to establish as a popular tourist destination in Bangladesh. In this research also tried to identify the important factors that can make more interest of tourist to satisfy. Major problems of tourism in Cox'sbazar are the lack proper planning, lack of infrastructural development facilities, safety and security, lack of update information and marketing policies. The Government should take initiatives to overcome these problems by developing infrastructural facilities, establishing some training program related to tourism, announcing tourist and Wi-Fi zone. The Government can introduce at Cox'sbazar as beach tourism, culture and heritage tourism, and rural tourism. So that is no so far that Cox'sbazar is the next prospective tourist spot from where country can earn more foreign currencies.

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Annexure

No	Name of Tourist Destination	Area (square per kilometer)	Away from Cox'sbazar Town
01	Laboni beach	125km (whole area)	2km
02	Kolatoli beach	125km (whole area)	2.5km
03	Himchari	1,729 hectares	18km
04	Inani beach	18km	35km
05	Ramu	391.71km	16km
06	Aggmeda Khyang Monastery:	100 feet high	15km
07	Maheshkhali	268km	12km
08	Teknaf	388.68km	80km
09	St. Martin's Island	10km	11okm
10	Sonadia Island	9km	9km
11	Dulhazra Safari Park	2,224 acres	50km

Figure- 3: Distance of Tourists Spot from Cox'sbazar Town

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